

Improving the Legal Framework on Financial Autonomy for Public Universities in Vietnam from the Perspective of Transaction Cost Theory

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Abstract

This study applies Transaction Cost Economics, initiated by Ronald Coase and developed by Oliver Williamson, to analyze and propose ways to improve the legal framework for financial autonomy of public universities in Vietnam. In the context of the Higher Education Law of 2025, effective from January 1, 2026, and its implementing guidelines, the Transaction Cost Theory approach allows for the identification of transaction costs arising in the relationship between the State, higher education institutions, and students, such as information costs, compliance costs, monitoring costs, and accountability costs. Based on an analysis of regulations on revenue generation, financial resource utilization, public asset management, and accountability, the article argues that the effectiveness of financial autonomy depends not only on the level of empowerment but also on the quality of institutional design. Therefore, the study proposes improving the legal framework towards greater consistency, transparency, stability, and enhanced autonomy coupled with accountability.

Keywords: *Financial autonomy, Public universities, Transaction cost theory.*

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Introduction

University autonomy is a key reform direction for Vietnamese higher education, with financial autonomy playing a central role as it is directly linked to the ability of public higher education institutions to mobilize, allocate, and utilize resources. In recent years, the law has gradually expanded the autonomy of universities, while also placing higher demands on transparency, accountability, and responsibility. However, there remains a significant gap between the autonomy enshrined in law and the ability to exercise that autonomy in practice.

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From this practical experience, the question arises not only about what rights the law has granted to universities, but more importantly, how the law is being designed so that those rights can be exercised effectively and substantially. A legal framework may expand autonomy in principle, but if it simultaneously creates too many procedures, complex coordination mechanisms, unclear responsibilities, or significant legal risks, then that very framework will reduce the effectiveness of financial autonomy. In other words, the effectiveness of financial autonomy depends not only on the scope of the rights granted, but also on the legal and institutional costs that higher education institutions must bear in exercising those rights.

It is at this point that Transaction Cost Theory provides a suitable approach to analyzing the legal framework for financial autonomy in public universities. This theoretical framework allows for the consideration of the law not only as a system of regulations allocating rights and obligations, but also as a tool to reduce the costs incurred in the interaction between the State, higher education institutions, and students. In the field of financial autonomy, these costs can manifest as information costs, procedural compliance costs, management coordination costs, monitoring costs, and accountability costs. When these costs are excessively high, the autonomy enshrined in law may be significantly curtailed in terms of implementation.

Although university autonomy and financial autonomy have attracted considerable research attention, most current studies primarily approach the issue from the perspective of public policy, university governance, or regulatory content analysis. Meanwhile, the Transaction Cost Theory approach to improving legislation on financial autonomy for public universities in Vietnam has not been fully explored. Based on this, this paper analyzes current legislation on financial autonomy for public universities from the perspective of Transaction Cost Theory, clarifies key institutional bottlenecks, and proposes directions for improving legislation to ensure genuine autonomy coupled with accountability and efficient use of financial resources.

Theoretical Basis of Transaction Costs and Their Implications for the Law on Financial Autonomy of Public Universities

Overview of Transaction Cost Theory

Transaction Cost Theory is one of the important approaches in institutional economics, originating from Ronald Coase's 1937 work, **The Nature of the Firm** (Coase, 1937). From the question of why businesses exist instead of all activities being carried out through the market, Coase argued that using market mechanisms is not without cost; on the contrary, entities must incur certain costs to seek information, negotiate, sign, and secure transactions. These costs are collectively called transaction costs (Wang, 2003). Building on Coase's ideas, Oliver Williamson further developed Transaction Cost Theory into an analytical framework for choosing governance structures, emphasizing that institutions and laws play a special role in reducing friction arising during interactions between entities (Williamson, 1981).

In essence, transaction costs can be understood as all costs incurred not from the production of goods or services themselves, but from the process of organizing, coordinating, securing, and controlling transactional relationships between entities. Later studies often distinguish between pre-transaction costs (ex ante) and post-transaction costs (ex post). (Renger & Czirfusz, 2022). Ex-ante costs include information gathering costs, partner outreach costs, negotiation and agreement

building costs (Renger & Czirfusz, 2022) ; while ex-post costs include monitoring costs, breach handling costs, contract adjustment costs, dispute resolution costs and losses incurred when the transaction is not performed as expected (Mori, 2013) .

This theory is also based on two fundamental behavioral assumptions. First, limited rationality, according to which subjects cannot have complete information and are unable to foresee all possible scenarios (Williamson, 1979) . Second, opportunism, that is, the possibility of parties pursuing their own interests in bad faith, through concealing information, evading obligations, or exploiting institutional loopholes (Williamson, 1979) . These two assumptions suggest that transactions cannot function effectively without sufficiently clear, stable, and feasible legal frameworks.

In the field of law concerning the financial autonomy of public universities, transaction costs are not only economic costs in the narrow sense, but also institutional costs arising in the relationship between the State, higher education institutions, students, and related entities. Therefore, approaching financial autonomy from the perspective of transaction costs allows for a deeper assessment of the quality of the current legal framework.

The Role of Legal Institutions in Reducing or Increasing Transaction Costs

From the perspective of Transaction Cost Theory, law plays a dual role. On the one hand, law is an important institution that helps reduce transaction costs by clearly establishing the rights and obligations of entities, standardizing processes, ensuring the enforcement of commitments, enhancing information transparency, and creating stability in the legal environment. When legal regulations are clear, consistent, and predictable, entities will reduce the costs of information searching, negotiation, supervision, and dispute risks (Famulski, 2017) . For the financial autonomy of public universities, good law must create a sufficiently clear institutional framework so that universities know what they are allowed to do, what procedures to follow, what their responsibilities are, and what mechanisms protect them.

On the other hand, laws can also become a source of increased transaction costs if poorly designed. Overlapping regulations, cumbersome administrative procedures, ambiguous legal standards, a "request-and-grant" mechanism, frequent policy instability, or the dispersion of authority among multiple entities can all increase search costs, compliance costs, coordination costs, and transaction delay costs. (Libecap, 2018) . In the field of financial autonomy for public universities, this is the reason why many autonomous rights, although recognized in name, are difficult to implement effectively in practice.

From this, it can be seen that the quality of law is not only assessed by its constitutionality, legality, or the intrinsic logic of its provisions, but also by its ability to reduce transaction costs for the relevant parties. This is also an important theoretical basis for applying Transaction Cost Theory to the study and improvement of laws on financial autonomy for public universities in Vietnam.

The Applicability of Transaction Cost Theory to the Field of Public Higher Education

Theoretical basis for applying Transaction Cost Theory to the public sector and higher education

Financial autonomy in public universities is a complex institutional space in which many stakeholders interact, including the State, higher education institutions, students, faculty, businesses, investors, research partners, and inspection and auditing agencies.

These relationships are not simply individual administrative or civil relations, but rather a totality of transactions with specific characteristics, simultaneously generating information costs, negotiation costs, monitoring costs, compliance costs, and accountability costs. Therefore, Transaction Cost Theory has a basis for application as an analytical framework to explain the operational structure of financial autonomy in public universities.

An important argument to be established is that Transaction Cost Theory is not only applicable to the private sector but can be extended to the public sector, including higher education. Williamson (1999), in his study on the relationship between public administration and transaction cost economics, pointed out that public authorities are also a transactional governance structure, and evaluating its effectiveness cannot be separated from the requirements of public integrity, public service accountability, and the feasibility of alternative institutional options (Williamson, 1999). Accordingly, the public sector is not excluded from the scope of explanation of Transaction Cost Theory; on the contrary, it is a sector particularly in need of this approach because public transactions are often associated with high uncertainty, large monitoring costs, and strict accountability requirements.

Subsequent review studies have also confirmed that Transaction Cost Theory has been widely applied in many fields outside of business, such as political science, law, public policy, agriculture, and healthcare (Macher & Richman, 2008). This shows the theory's potential to extend beyond explaining the existence of businesses or the choice between market and organization, to evaluating models of public governance in which law plays a fundamental institutional role.

For higher education, the relevance of Transaction Cost Theory is even more evident because it is not a purely market but a partial market, where market mechanisms operate only within limits and are always associated with public intervention (Ortegat, 2024). Higher education possesses both the characteristics of a public service and contains elements of market exchange such as tuition fees, training contracts, research cooperation, technology transfer, service provision, and asset exploitation. In this environment, market failures such as information asymmetry, positive externalities, and the difficulty of learners in fully assessing the quality of education make transaction costs a central variable in institutional design (Ortegat, 2024). Therefore, applying Transaction Cost Theory to the field of public higher education is justified both theoretically and practically.

The applicability of Transaction Cost Theory in the subject relationships of financial autonomy in public universities.

a) The relationship between the State and public higher education institutions

This is the central relationship of financial autonomy for public universities, and also the relationship that best illustrates the logic of transaction costs. In this relationship, the State plays the role of the authorizing party, allocating budgets, assigning tasks, and establishing the legal framework; while the public higher education institution is the party empowered to carry out the tasks of training, research, and serving society (Kivistö, 2005). This relationship is typical of information asymmetry and conflict of objectives, because the State finds it difficult to fully grasp the actual training costs, the efficiency of resource utilization, or the quality of output of each school (Kivistö, 2008).

From a transaction cost perspective, this relationship simultaneously gives rise to costs of information retrieval, negotiation costs regarding the level of autonomy, monitoring

costs, costs due to adverse selection, moral hazard, and opportunity costs due to lengthy approval procedures (Dixit, 2003; Kivistö, 2008; Kivistö & Zalyevska, 2015; Williamson, 1991) . In particular, information asymmetry in the relationship between the State and higher education institutions is not accidental but structural, because the products of universities are results that are difficult to measure directly, such as the quality of training, research results, and value in serving society (Dixit, 2003) . This explains why laws on financial autonomy cannot stop at decentralization, but must also design mechanisms for budget allocation, control, accountability, and incentives to balance benefits, information, and motivation. (Lane & Kivisto, 2008) .

Therefore, applying Transaction Cost Theory reveals that the quality of laws on financial autonomy depends significantly on whether those laws help reduce information costs, monitoring costs, opportunity costs, and limit opportunistic behavior in the exercise of autonomy.

b) The relationship between higher education institutions and students

The relationship between higher education institutions and students is characterized by a very high degree of information asymmetry. Higher education services are a type of service whose quality is difficult for students to accurately assess; that is, students cannot fully evaluate the quality of the service not only before participating but also after consuming it (Jongbloed, 2003; Ortegat, 2024) . This gives rise to a series of specific transaction costs, primarily the cost of searching for and processing information, as students must collect, compare, and evaluate information about training programs, tuition fees, faculty quality, employment rates, and degree value in a context of incomplete information.

Furthermore, in the context of increasing tuition fee autonomy, learners also face the cost of evaluating the correlation between the cost incurred and the value received, which is a form of indirect negotiation cost in the choice of educational services (Woodall et al., 2012) . The marketization of the relationship between schools and students, if taken too far, can also lead to opportunity costs and hidden costs related to output quality, learning motivation, and educational orientation. At the same time, the increasing role of learners in an autonomous environment also creates a need for reverse monitoring mechanisms, that is, tools for learners to evaluate, provide feedback, and demand accountability from educational institutions (Reynolds, 2022) .

From a legal perspective, applying Transaction Cost Theory to this relationship demonstrates the need to establish a mechanism for mandatory information disclosure, set transparent standards regarding tuition fees, training quality, and accountability, and improve mechanisms for protecting students' rights in the context of increasing financial autonomy.

c) The relationship between higher education institutions and faculty members

The relationship between higher education institutions and faculty is one that is highly specific to human assets. Faculty members must make long-term investments in specialized knowledge, research capabilities, curricula, academic networks, and teaching experience, while the value of these investments is often closely tied to the specific institutional and professional environment of each institution (Morita & Tang, 2017) . Under these circumstances, labor relations in universities cannot be viewed as a typical labor transaction, but rather as a long-term relationship with a high degree of interdependence.

From the perspective of Transaction Cost Theory, this relationship generates considerable costs, particularly monitoring costs and the costs of establishing appropriate binding mechanisms. This is because the work performance of faculty members, such as teaching quality, mentoring ability, research contributions, or academic value, is difficult to measure accurately using simple indicators (Morita & Tang, 2017) . If the law and internal governance mechanisms are too heavily skewed towards short-term contracts or focus solely on incentives based on output, this can create negative reactions from faculty members, while simultaneously increasing transaction costs and reducing the quality of labor relations in universities (Morita & Tang, 2017) .

The Transaction Cost Theory suggests that legislation on financial autonomy should not only focus on expanding the decision-making power of higher education institutions regarding salaries, income, and benefits, but also ensure the professional stability of faculty and design governance mechanisms that are appropriate to the unique characteristics of academic activity.

d) Relationships between higher education institutions and businesses, investors, and research partners

Collaborative relationships between higher education institutions and businesses, investors, and research partners are a typical hybrid transaction according to Williamson's classification, meaning they do not operate entirely according to market mechanisms but are also not entirely within a hierarchical organizational model (Williamson, 1991) . This is an increasingly important area for the financial autonomy of public universities, as it is directly linked to the ability to diversify revenue sources, commercialize research results, and connect universities with the practical needs of the economy (Ebers & Oerlemans, 2016) .

However, this type of relationship also gives rise to many specific transaction costs. First, there are the costs of finding a suitable partner, due to differences in organizational culture, operational goals, and operating methods between the academic and business sectors (Qiu et al., 2024) . Next are the costs of negotiating and signing contracts, especially in matters related to intellectual property rights, profit sharing, information security, and specialized investments (Qiu et al., 2024) . When parties have invested in specialized assets, the risk of one party exploiting the other's dependence increases, requiring the presence of more complex guarantee mechanisms and contract governance structures than typical market transactions (Beamish & Sharp, 2001) .

The application of Transaction Cost Theory to this relationship is significant for improving legislation, as it highlights the need to build a clear, stable, and flexible legal framework for cooperation between universities and businesses, particularly in issues of intellectual property rights, dispute resolution mechanisms, intellectual property exploitation rights, and the model of intermediary legal entities such as businesses formed from the commercialization of university research results.

e) Relationship between higher education institutions and inspection, auditing, and control agencies

The relationship between higher education institutions and inspection, auditing, and control agencies is a direct manifestation of supervisory costs in the Transaction Cost Theory model (Williamson, 1991) . In a financially autonomous system, this relationship is necessary to ensure the proper use of public resources, enhance accountability, and limit abuses of autonomy. However, supervisory activities themselves generate considerable costs during implementation.

In this relationship, the most obvious cost is the compliance cost. Higher education institutions must dedicate considerable time, manpower, and resources to reporting, preparing documents, working with inspection teams, fulfilling inspection requirements, and meeting audit standards. In addition, there are costs associated with measuring effectiveness, as the quality of training and the impact of research activities are difficult to quantify accurately. When relying heavily on representative indicators, evaluations may be biased towards chasing statistics rather than reflecting true quality. If the control mechanism is designed too tightly or procedures are lengthy, opportunity costs also increase, as universities will find it difficult to respond promptly to societal needs and new development opportunities (Dixit, 2003) .

From this, it can be seen that Transaction Cost Theory is particularly significant in evaluating the rationality of laws on inspection, auditing, and financial control in universities. The issue is not only about strengthening accountability, but also about designing a monitoring mechanism that balances the compliance costs borne by educational institutions. In this direction, improving the law should be based on a comparison between the current control mechanism and other more feasible options, meaning that changes should only be made when a truly better solution exists in practice (Williamson, 1999) .

Overall, applying Transaction Cost Theory to the field of financial autonomy in public universities is appropriate, as this is a field with many intertwined relationships, incomplete information, and transaction costs arising at various stages. This approach shows that laws on financial autonomy not only need to define the rights and responsibilities of the entities, but also must be designed to reduce transaction costs, in accordance with the nature of each specific relationship. Based on this, Transaction Cost Theory provides a valuable analytical framework for improving the laws on financial autonomy in public universities in Vietnam.

Legal Framework for Analyzing Financial Autonomy in Public Universities from the Perspective of Transaction Costs

Establishing and mobilizing financial resources

Establishing and mobilizing financial resources is a fundamental aspect of financial autonomy for public universities. Legally, this includes the right to collect tuition fees, provide training services, conduct scientific research, transfer technology, exploit research results, receive funding, donations, loans, and establish cooperative relationships with external entities. According to the European University Association's Autonomy Scorecard, financial autonomy is typically reflected in rights such as determining tuition fees, retaining the difference from the state budget, borrowing and raising capital in the financial market; at the same time, the level of financial autonomy is closely related to the ability of higher education institutions to diversify their revenue sources (Estermann et al., 2011; Estermann & Nokkala, 2009; Estermann & Steinel, 2011) .

From a transaction cost perspective, this group of issues needs to be considered not only in terms of the scope of the rights granted, but also in terms of the costs incurred during the exercise of those rights. Each type of revenue source or form of capital mobilization can generate different transaction costs, such as information costs, negotiation costs, contract signing and execution costs, and costs of ensuring trust between the parties (Johnstone, 2003, 2004) . Therefore, the legal framework in this area needs to both facilitate public higher education institutions in expanding their

financial resources and limit barriers that increase transaction costs (Phuong Anh, 2025) .

Management, allocation, and exploitation of public financial resources and assets.

Another important legal aspect of financial autonomy for public universities is the right to manage, allocate, and utilize existing resources. This includes the right to prepare and implement internal budgets, allocate expenditures, use the difference between revenue and expenditure, reinvest in training and research, decide on salary and benefits policies, and also includes the right to manage, use, and exploit public assets such as land, buildings, laboratories, equipment, trademarks, and intellectual property (Decree No. 60/2021/ND-CP, 2021) .

From a transaction cost perspective, this group of factors directly reflects the actual level of autonomy of public higher education institutions. A lack of flexibility in resource allocation, excessive reliance on external approval mechanisms, or ambiguity regarding the right to exploit public assets can all increase adaptation costs, internal monitoring costs, waiting costs, and opportunity costs. (Kivistö, 2008) . Regarding public assets, the issue is that if management rights are not accompanied by appropriate exploitation mechanisms, many resources may not be used effectively, thereby reducing the real value of financial autonomy. Therefore, the legal framework in this area needs to ensure that public higher education institutions have sufficient capacity to proactively manage and exploit resources, while remaining within the necessary control limits.

Transparency, accountability, and financial control mechanisms.

Transparency, accountability, and financial control mechanisms are essential components of financial autonomy for public universities. Legally, this includes the obligation to disclose tuition fees, revenue and expenditure, financial reporting, operational results, accountability to management agencies, students, and society, and subject to supervision through inspections, audits, and related accreditation mechanisms (Adeusi et al., 2024) .

From a transaction cost perspective, transparency is significant in reducing information asymmetry between entities, thereby contributing to lower information retrieval costs, monitoring costs, and appraisal costs. However, fulfilling these obligations also generates information production costs, compliance costs, and monitoring costs. If the control mechanism is designed to be overly overlapping, formalistic, or imposes excessive procedural burdens, compliance costs can increase to the point of undermining the effectiveness of financial autonomy (JM Consulting Ltd, 2005; Vanderbilt University, 2015) . Therefore, within this area, the requirement for the legal framework is to ensure accountability while simultaneously avoiding excessive control costs.

Current Situation and Legal Assessment of Financial Autonomy for Public Universities in Vietnam from the Perspective of Transaction Costs

Current legal framework and initial results

The current legal framework governing financial autonomy for public universities in Vietnam is based on the Law on Higher Education 2025 (Law No. 125/2025/QH15), effective from January 1, 2026. This law redefines the autonomy of higher education institutions, emphasizing proactive decision-making coupled with accountability; it also recognizes the autonomy of higher education institutions in academic,

organizational, personnel, financial, asset, and other higher education activities. Furthermore, Articles 38, 39, and 41 of the law establish a direct legal basis for the financial mechanism, funding sources, and tuition fees for public higher education institutions. (Legal Law on Higher Education, 2025) .

However, this legal framework comprises not only the 2025 Higher Education Law but also many related documents. First, Decree No. 60/2021/ND-CP remains an important basis for the financial autonomy mechanism of public non-profit organizations. Next, Decree No. 238/2025/ND-CP regulates tuition fees, exemptions, reductions, and support for tuition fees and service prices in the field of education and training, replacing the previous tuition fee mechanism under Decree No. 81/2021/ND-CP and Decree No. 97/2023/ND-CP. Furthermore, the implementation of financial autonomy by public universities is also governed by the 2017 Law on Management and Use of Public Assets and the 2015 Law on State Budget, which set limits, conditions, and control mechanisms for the management and use of public resources. Therefore, it can be said that the financial autonomy of public universities in Vietnam is currently regulated by an interdisciplinary system of regulations, in which the Higher Education Law of 2025 plays a foundational role, while Decree No. 60/2021/ND-CP, Decree No. 238/2025/ND-CP, the Law on Management and Use of Public Assets of 2017, and the State Budget Law of 2015 play a role in specifying, limiting, and controlling the practical implementation of autonomy.

Based on that legal framework, several initial results can be noted. First, the autonomy mechanism has promoted innovation in internal governance within public higher education institutions. By August 2023, 170 out of 174 public higher education institutions had established and operationalized their school councils, achieving a rate of 97.4%, including all 36 units under the Ministry of Education and Training. Prior to that, by the end of 2017, 23 public universities had received approval from the Prime Minister for pilot projects on comprehensive autonomy, committing to self-financing both recurrent and investment expenditures. By 2022, based on reports from 141 out of 232 higher education institutions, over 80% of the universities implementing in-depth autonomy in admissions and training recorded positive operational results; At the same time, over 65% of universities implementing deep autonomy in science and technology also achieved good results. These figures show that current legislation has initially created an institutional foundation for the transition from an administrative management model to a university governance model with clearer decentralization of power and responsibility (Thao, 2023) .

Secondly, the current legal framework has facilitated the diversification of revenue sources for public higher education institutions and gradually reduced their dependence on the state budget. The financial autonomy mechanism allows universities to be more proactive in budget management, while expanding non-budgetary revenue sources through diversification of professional activities, joint ventures, partnerships, and collaborations. The practices at Hanoi National University and Ho Chi Minh City National University show that these institutions have gradually built diverse revenue sources, forming sustainable development funds, financial reserve funds, and development investment funds, thereby reducing the pressure of sudden tuition fee increases. (Truong, 2025) . By 2024, 13 universities achieved revenue of VND 1,000 billion or more, an increase of 2 universities compared to the previous year (Tam, 2025) . From a transaction cost perspective, this is a positive development as it helps higher education institutions reduce their dependence on a single source of

funding, thereby reducing financial risk and improving their adaptability to policy changes.

Thirdly, autonomy has also initially led to improvements in the quality of training and research. The practice at the Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City shows an increase in the number of international publications, more internationally accredited programs, and a rise in the number of universities included in international rankings (Uyen, 2024). As of August 2023, 261 training institutions had completed external evaluations according to domestic standards, 194 training institutions had received official accreditation, and 9 training institutions had received accreditation according to foreign standards (Thao, 2023). These results show that financial autonomy not only impacts resources but also creates conditions for higher education institutions to increase investment in quality and academic competitiveness.

Fourth, autonomy also promotes innovation in internal governance. Survey results from a sample of 593 participants showed statistically significant differences in most of the 7 research areas between autonomous and non-autonomous universities, reflecting the clear impact of autonomy policies. For academic autonomy, the average score across the system reached 3.90/5 (SD = 0.17), the highest among the four dimensions of autonomy: academic, organizational, personnel, and financial; this indicates that academic autonomy has been granted more strongly, while financial autonomy remains at a lower level (Pham et al., 2022). Regarding governance, the practice at the Vietnam National University Ho Chi Minh City shows a trend towards shifting from input control to output-based management, while simultaneously building a system of quantitative criteria to monitor the quality of training and research.

Current legislation has laid a relatively clear foundation for financial autonomy in public universities, while also yielding some initial results in governance reform, revenue diversification, improved training and research quality, and enhanced accountability. From a transaction cost perspective, these results show that the law has contributed to reducing some of the costs of application, waiting, coordination, and information in some basic activities of public higher education institutions. However, these results are still uneven across universities and only reflect the initial transition phase, thus requiring further consideration of the limitations of current legislation in the following section.

Main limitations of current legislation from the perspective of transaction costs

From the perspective of transaction cost theory, the quality of legislation is measured not only by whether it empowers individuals or entities, but also by its ability to reduce the total costs incurred by stakeholders in exercising those rights legally, effectively, and predictably. In the field of financial autonomy for public universities, legislation not only allocates rights and obligations between the State, higher education institutions, students, and related stakeholders, but also designs the institutional environment for financial transactions, investments, collaborations, asset exploitation, and accountability to operate. Therefore, when the legal framework lacks uniformity, is overly procedural, unstable, or does not clearly define the decision-making mechanism, transaction costs will increase not only in the implementation phase but also in the preparation, coordination, and risk forecasting phases. Based on this criterion, current legislation on financial autonomy for public universities in Vietnam still reveals five main limitations.

Firstly, legal regulations are overlapping and inconsistent. This is a pervasive limitation because the financial autonomy of public universities is not only governed by the 2025

Higher Education Law but is also directly linked to laws on the autonomy mechanism of public service units, tuition fees, public property, state budget, and other related public finance regulations. In this context, higher education institutions often face not just a single regulatory framework, but must operate within a multi-layered network of regulations with multiple points of contact, which are not always compatible. From a transaction cost perspective, this increases information and coordination costs: universities must allocate additional resources to research, compare, seek opinions, determine priority documents to apply, and mitigate legal risks. At a deeper level, this overlapping phenomenon reflects a theoretical problem: the legal system has not been designed to optimize transactions, but rather favors fragmented management across different sectors. Consequently, while autonomy is expanded in terms of legal documents, it is in practice "held back" by layers of inconsistently operating legal limitations.

Secondly, the control mechanism remains heavily reliant on pre-approval, increasing compliance costs and opportunity costs. In principle, control over public finances and assets is necessary to ensure public objectives and prevent opportunistic behavior. However, the issue lies not in the existence of control, but in its scope and manner. When too many financial transactions of higher education institutions, including routine operational transactions, require external approval steps, compliance costs increase significantly. This includes not only direct costs in terms of time, manpower, and procedures, but also opportunity costs due to delays in signing cooperation agreements, implementing projects, exploiting assets, or mobilizing resources at the right time. From a transaction cost perspective, this is a manifestation of an institutional structure where pre-approval mechanisms overshadow post-approval mechanisms. At that time, the law prioritized preventing management risks from the outset, but this significantly reduced the flexibility and adaptability that are the core meaning of financial autonomy.

Thirdly, autonomy, accountability, and internal governance mechanisms have not been truly integrated. Theoretically, financial autonomy for public universities is a multi-layered delegation relationship: the State empowers higher education institutions to be more proactive in resource utilization, while simultaneously maintaining accountability and control mechanisms to ensure public objectives are met. To achieve this, autonomy must be linked to a sufficiently clear, stable, and capable internal governance structure. However, in current legislation, the compatibility between autonomy, accountability, responsibility, and internal governance mechanisms is not yet clearly defined. In particular, the changes to the governance model of public higher education institutions under the 2025 Higher Education Law necessitate a re-establishment of internal financial decision-making and oversight mechanisms within the institution based on a new legal framework. If financial autonomy is not accompanied by a sufficiently transparent internal governance mechanism capable of clearly defining responsibilities, agency costs, supervisory costs, and uncertainty costs will increase. In other words, financial autonomy without a corresponding governance structure easily falls into a situation where authority is granted nominally, but its effectiveness depends on the flexibility of each individual institution and entity.

Fourth, the tuition fee framework and financial mechanisms still lack the necessary stability and predictability. In transaction cost theory, an unstable institutional environment increases adaptation costs because stakeholders cannot reliably predict the conditions for making investment, cooperation, or resource allocation decisions in the medium and long term. The financial autonomy of public universities in Vietnam

is currently still clearly affected by this phenomenon. Although the Higher Education Law of 2025 has established the principle of tuition fees to cover costs and allow for reasonable accumulation, implementation still depends on government regulations and guiding documents. In practice, the tuition fee mechanism and financial autonomy mechanism have undergone numerous adjustments in a short period, making it difficult for higher education institutions to develop stable financial strategies. Consequently, decisions requiring a long-term perspective, such as investing in infrastructure, developing new training programs, recruiting high-quality personnel, or expanding research collaborations, all face a higher degree of uncertainty. From a transaction cost perspective, this is a fundamental limitation as it directly impacts the university's ability to plan for and sustain long-term transactions.

Fifth, administrative management thinking remains strongly dominant, and transaction costs have not yet become a criterion for evaluating the quality of legislation. This is the deepest structural limitation. Although current legislation has acknowledged greater autonomy than before, the design of many regulations is still primarily based on the logic of administrative safety, that is, prioritizing the prevention of wrongdoing, the protection of public assets, and the minimization of risks from the perspective of the management agency. This approach has some merit, but if it does not simultaneously consider the costs incurred by subjects to exercise their rights, it can easily lead to a situation where the law is "correct in terms of management" but "institutionally costly." Here, transaction costs have not been used as a technical criterion to assess the quality of legal norms. Therefore, many regulations, while reasonable in terms of administrative form, increase information costs, compliance costs, coordination costs, and opportunity costs in practice. As a result, financial autonomy has been expanded on paper, but the extent of its realization remains limited by the very way the law is designed.

Orientations and Solutions for Improving the Legal Framework on Financial Autonomy of Public Universities from the Perspective of Transaction Cost Theory

Orientation for Improving the Legal Framework on Financial Autonomy of Public Universities

The starting point for improving the legal framework on financial autonomy for public universities is to view the law not only as a tool for empowering them, but also as an institution that helps entities exercise that power at a reasonable cost, in a stable, transparent, and predictable environment. From a transaction cost approach, the issue is not just how broadly autonomy is recognized, but also whether that power can be effectively implemented in practice. This requirement becomes even clearer in the context of significant changes to the legal framework on financial autonomy for public universities with the 2025 Higher Education Law, Decree No. 111/2025/ND-CP amending Decree No. 60/2021/ND-CP, and Decree No. 238/2025/ND-CP on tuition fees.

Firstly, it is necessary to ensure genuine financial autonomy. While the law may grant higher education institutions the right to decide on revenue, expenditure, asset management, investment, and resource mobilization, if the exercise of these rights still involves too many layers of conditions, procedures, or overlapping approvals, then autonomy will only exist in name. Therefore, it is necessary to further define each right

of financial autonomy with sufficiently specific regulations that can be directly implemented, thereby narrowing the gap between recognized rights and the ability to implement them in practice.

Secondly, it is necessary to reduce transaction costs arising from unnecessary legal procedures. In transaction cost theory, procedures are only meaningful when they help reduce risk and standardize transactions; if procedures are too broad, too multi-layered, or disproportionate to the level of risk, they will increase compliance costs, waiting costs, and opportunity costs. Therefore, the law needs to redesign procedures according to the principle of proportionality: ordinary transactions, small value, and low risk should gradually shift to a notification, public disclosure, and post-audit mechanism; while large-value, high-risk transactions should require stricter prior approval.

Thirdly, it is necessary to harmonize multi-sectoral legislation related to the financial autonomy of public universities. Currently, autonomy is stipulated in higher education law, but its implementation is simultaneously governed by laws on public service units, tuition fees, public assets, the state budget, and other public financial regulations. When these documents are incompatible, implementing entities not only incur compliance costs but also bear additional costs for research, comparison, and coordination. Therefore, improving the law should aim to ensure consistency among related regulatory groups, while clearly establishing the principles of application when conflicts arise between higher education law and other specialized laws.

Fourth, there needs to be a strong shift from pre-auditing to post-auditing. In the public sector, control is necessary to ensure institutional integrity, protect public assets, and maintain accountability. However, if too many financial decisions of higher education institutions require prior approval, waiting costs and opportunity costs will increase, undermining the meaning of autonomy. Therefore, the control mechanism needs to be redesigned to reduce input control over routine transactions while strengthening output oversight through financial reporting, information disclosure, auditing, accreditation, and sanctions for violations.

Fifth, expanding autonomy must be closely linked to transparency and accountability. From a transaction cost perspective, autonomy and accountability are not contradictory: autonomy enhances adaptability, while transparency and accountability reduce information asymmetry, lower monitoring costs, and limit opportunistic behavior. Therefore, expanding autonomy is only sustainable when accompanied by mechanisms for publicly disclosing information on tuition fees, financial status, quality assurance, and resource utilization efficiency, while clearly establishing levels of accountability to students, society, management agencies, and the public.

Solutions for Improving the Legal Framework on Financial Autonomy of Public Universities from the Perspective of Transaction Cost Theory

Refine regulations on the scope and extent of financial autonomy.

The first solution is to further refine regulations on the scope and extent of financial autonomy for public higher education institutions, clarifying the meaning of autonomy. The current issue is not only whether the law recognizes financial autonomy, but also how specifically that autonomy is defined to be directly implemented in practice. Therefore, the law needs to more clearly define the rights of public higher education institutions in creating, allocating, and using legitimate revenue sources, managing assets, investing in development, and mobilizing resources. Only when the scope of rights is sufficiently clearly defined will financial autonomy move

beyond mere formality and become a truly functioning mechanism. From a transaction cost perspective, this solution is significant in reducing legal search costs, regulatory interpretation costs, and institutional risk costs arising from legal ambiguity.

Improving the legal framework on tuition fees and mechanisms for generating revenue.

The second solution is to improve the legal framework regarding tuition fees and revenue generation mechanisms to enhance the stability, transparency, and predictability of university financial policies. Currently, tuition fees remain a crucial source of revenue for public higher education institutions, but frequent changes in tuition policies or a lack of a clear roadmap will increase adaptation costs and impair the ability of universities to plan their medium- and long-term finances. Therefore, a tuition fee mechanism needs to be developed that is more stable, transparent, and closely linked to actual training costs and the responsibility for improving quality. Simultaneously, the law should expand the legal scope for revenue sources beyond tuition fees, especially revenue from scientific research, technology transfer, cooperation with businesses, service provision, and legitimate fundraising. From a transaction cost perspective, this solution not only reduces reliance on a single revenue source but also helps reduce uncertainty, negotiation, and adaptation costs in the process of securing funding for public higher education institutions.

Improving the legal framework for public assets in public universities.

The third solution is to improve the legal framework for the management, use, and exploitation of public assets in public higher education institutions. Currently, one of the reasons for the high transaction costs is the complexity of procedures for exploiting public assets, the broad scope of pre-auditing, and the fact that the application mechanism does not clearly distinguish between different types of transactions. Therefore, it is necessary to simplify procedures for exploiting public assets by clearly classifying which activities require pre-auditing and which can be shifted to post-auditing. For ordinary transactions with small values, low risk, and no impact on the public purpose of the asset, the law should allow for a more flexible mechanism; conversely, for transactions with large values, high risk, or directly related to strategically significant public assets, strict control should still be maintained. At the same time, it is necessary to build appropriate legal mechanisms so that public higher education institutions can effectively utilize existing facilities, laboratories, intellectual property, and resources while ensuring the prevention of loss, abuse, and misuse for public purposes. From a transaction cost perspective, this solution helps reduce approval costs, waiting costs, and legal risk costs in the exploitation of public assets.

Improving internal governance mechanisms linked to financial responsibility.

The fourth solution is to improve the internal governance mechanism linked to financial accountability. Financial autonomy can only operate effectively when placed within a clear governance structure, where decision-making authority, implementation authority, and accountability are clearly defined. Therefore, the law needs to further clarify the financial decision-making mechanism within public higher education institutions, clearly identifying the authority responsible for decision-making, implementation, and accountability. Along with this, it is necessary to improve the quality of internal control, strengthen internal auditing, and clearly define individual responsibilities in the use of financial resources. From a transaction cost perspective, this solution is significant in reducing agency costs, dispute costs, monitoring costs, and coordination costs within public higher education institutions. Simultaneously, it

also helps increase consistency and predictability in the financial decision-making process.

Improving mechanisms for openness, transparency, and accountability.

The fifth solution is to improve the mechanisms of openness, transparency, and accountability by standardizing financial disclosure obligations and increasing access to information for students, society, and relevant stakeholders. In the context of financial autonomy, openness and accountability are not only tools for controlling power, but also methods for reducing information asymmetry and building institutional trust. Therefore, the law needs to standardize the content to be disclosed, the form of disclosure, the timing of disclosure, and the responsibilities of the entities disclosing information regarding tuition fees, training costs, revenue-expenditure structure, resource utilization results, quality assurance status, and public asset exploitation. Simultaneously, a more effective accountability mechanism needs to be designed to reduce the need for direct external administrative intervention. In other words, when information is fully, accurately, and promptly disclosed, and when accountability is genuinely implemented, the need for control through administrative orders can be reasonably reduced. From a transaction cost perspective, this solution helps reduce information costs, monitoring costs, and limit unnecessary administrative interventions.

Conclusion

Financial autonomy is a core element of public university autonomy, as it is a crucial condition for higher education institutions to proactively manage their operations, improve the quality of education, and efficiently utilize resources. Vietnamese law has made significant progress in recognizing financial autonomy, but its implementation remains limited due to institutional barriers such as inconsistent regulations, complex administrative procedures, and a lack of truly flexible financial management mechanisms. Approaching from the perspective of Transaction Cost Theory, the issue is not just about expanding autonomy, but also about designing a legal framework capable of reducing transaction costs, cutting unnecessary procedures, increasing transparency, and improving the efficiency of resource allocation. Therefore, perfecting the law on financial autonomy for public universities needs to be done in a way that is consistent, transparent, stable, and ensures genuine autonomy.

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